

Experimental study of through the wall imaging for the detection of vital life signs using SFWR

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ABSTRACT

Now a day's defence applications associated to novel, army and military war fields are required wall imaging discrimination. As of now many wall-imaging techniques are designed but didn't identify the vital signs behind walls with accurate working. Therefore, a novel advance wall image tracking method is required identification of human target. An experimental study on through the wallimaging (TWI) to detect the life signs using sweep frequency continuous wave radar (SFCWR) is explained in this paper. The proposed system consists of agile vector network analyzer (VNA) (Agilent E5071B ENA), horn antenna and a computer. The information of heart beat and the breathing can be a shift identification routine was used to collect information from the back scattering electric current. The outcomes of the procedure give the information of heart beat and breathing signs of real human being.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Through-the-wall radar (TWR) is a new tool that can be used to track and locate unseen items hidden behind walls. It has a wide range of uses, including victim identification in evacuation and hostage situations, as well as human localization in anti-terrorist actions and life detection in earthquake debris [1]. Microwave doppler radars [2] have recently been designed for remote sensing of pulse and breathing. The incidence, phase, intensity, and delivery the time it takes for a live human body to return a signal can vary all be affected by pulse and breathing movements. Instead to the thickness and electrical assets of the wall content, these responses can be significantly reduced [2]. As a result, obtaining accurate radar-based identification of pulse or breathing is generally regarded as a difficult challenge. In this study, they used a phased frequency rf signals radar system with a large fractional bandwidth (50 percent) [3]. As a result, shift detection (CD) algorithms will identify human life signals hidden behind walls. Breathing is a repetitive behaviour that occurs at regular intervals. The subtraction of two consecutive data sets yields the discrepancy signals. On 2D time-varying range profile figure, the difference signal appears as the breathing's periodic behaviour. Pardhu and Kumar [3] clearly explained about the interfacing of radar to vector network analyzer (VNA) and receiving of echo [4]. Li *et al.* [5] explained about human identification using ultra-wideband (UWB) radar with low frequency. Where as we have done the identification using sweep frequency continuous wave radar (SFCWR) which operates at high frequency and also in multiple clutter situation.

2. RADAR SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

We used a monostatic setup in the presence of a insubstantial wall with a thickness of 30 cm in the tests. A C-band pyramidal array antenna was used as a monitor, and the Agilent E5071B ENA vector system analyser (VSA) frequency was changed from 3 to 5 GHz for 201 linearly treaded stages. Figure 1 depicts the experimental radar setup. Radar specifications that we are using in this experiment is given in in Table 1.

Figure 1. These figures are (a) experimental setup and (b) experimental setup model

Table 1. Radar parameters and specifications

Radar parameters as well as specifications		
S.No	Parameter	Specification
1	Frequency Range of Operation	1 GHz to 3 GHz
2	Power that is radiated	0dBm
3	Step Size of Frequency	10MHz
4	Amount of traces	1,024
5	Swept Time	0.024881 sec
6	Range Resolution in Air	7.5 cm

3. METHODOLOGY

Let transmitter and receiver of UWB radar are placed at x_t, x_r , while nominal chest position is at x_c and abdomen position is at x_a of stationary human target. The receiver signal $d(t)$ is obtained after abdomen and chest reflections of human objective positioned at d_0 is known by $d(t)$ and presented in Figure 2 [6]-[10].

Figure 2. Breathing model of human target

$$d(t) = d_0 + m_c(t) + m_a(t) \quad (1)$$

$$= d_0 + \sum_{i=1}^M c_i \sin(2\pi i f_h t) + \sum_{j=1}^N a_j \sin(2\pi j f_b t) \quad (2)$$

Where c_i, a_i represents harmonic components of displacement of chest and abdomen, f_b represents frequency of breathing & M, N represents count of significant components of abdomen and chest displacement. Displacement of heart is ignored as radar doesn't had sufficient resolution to detect heart motion. The output of the correlator can be represented as the variation due to abdomen and chest, the amount of the channel's multiple answers [11]-[15]:

$$r(t, \tau) = \sum_i A_i p(\tau - \tau_i) + A p(\tau - \tau_d(t)) \quad (3)$$

where $p(t)$ represents correlator output. A_i Gives correlator output related to the i^{th} static multipath component, τ_i represents delay. A Represents the correlator output related to reflections from body. $\tau_d(t)$ is

the time delay related with abdominal & chest movements and represented as a total of flight time τ_0 and two delays are represented as (4).

$$\tau_d(t) = \tau_0 + \sum_i^M \tau_i \sin(2\pi i f_b t) + \sum_j^N \mu_j \sin(2\pi j f_b t) \tag{4}$$

Where $\tau_0 = \frac{2d_0}{c} = \tau_i = \frac{2c_i}{c} \mu_j = \frac{2a_j}{c}$ and c is light's maximum speed. The experimented correlator in slow time, output is achieved in distinct instants. $t = kT_s, k = 1, \dots, K$ at discrete fast sample time $\tau = lT_f, l = 1, \dots, L$. As the static environment was considered static clutter component appeared as dendritic cells (DC) component and removed by pre-processing algorithm [4]. Let $y(t, \tau)$ be the uncluttered signal i.e it contains the information related to only abdomen and chest movement and is given by (5).

$$y(t, \tau) = Ap(\tau - \tau_0 - \sum_{i=1}^M \tau_i \sin(2\pi i f_b t) - \sum_{j=1}^N \mu_j \sin(2\pi j f_b t)) \tag{5}$$

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) shows chest and abdomen alive signals respectively. Figure 3(b) shows the displacements by abdomen cannot be ignored in all UWB radar human detection models [16]-[18]. Figure 4 show the densityfunctional theory (DFT) of recorded signals. It was observed in DFT of abdomen breathing signal that multiple frequency harmonics are present. This designates that the displacements of chest and abdomen are not sinusoidal. Let us consider that the movement of chest is sinusoidal and abdominal movement is semi sinusoidal [19]-[23]. We consider, the movement of chest is sinusoidal ($M=1$) and the abdominal movement possess the first harmonic (fundamental frequency) and the 2nd harmonic then (5) becomes.

$$y(t, \tau) = Ap(\tau - \tau_0 - (\tau_1 + \mu_1) \cdot \sin(2\pi_b t) - \mu_2 \sin(4\pi f_b t)) \tag{6}$$

Figure 3. These figures are (a) chest breathing signal and (b) abdomen breathing signal

Figure 4. DFT of abdomen breathing signal

The Fourier transform of $y(t, \tau)$ along the slow time can be represented as (7).

$$Y(f, z) = \int_{-x}^{+\pi} (t, \tau) e^{-z+t} dt \tag{7}$$

From 2-D Fourier transform (7) can be:

$$Y(f, \tau) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\pi} Y(f, v) e^{/2\pi t} dv \tag{8}$$

The 2-D Fourier Transform $Y(f, v)$ can be written as:

$$Y(f, v) = A(P(v)e^{-12mt_1} \int (S_1 S_2 S_3) e^{-12m} dt) \quad (9)$$

where $P(v)$ represents in the short time of the correlated Fourier transform output:

$$S_1 = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} j_k(\beta_{\tau_1} v) e^{-j2\pi k f t t} \quad (10)$$

$$S_2 = \sum_{l=-\infty}^{+\infty} j_l(\beta_{\mu_1} v) e^{-j2\pi f_b t} \quad (11)$$

$$S_3 = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{+\infty} j_m(\beta_{\mu_2} v) e^{-j2\pi m(2f_b)t} \quad (12)$$

where $\beta_x = 2\pi x$ and $\sum_{p=-\infty}^{+\infty} J_p(z) e^{-j2\pi p f t} = e^{-j \sin(2\pi f t)}$ is Bessel Functions of order n . After simplification it is shown that at $\tau = \tau_0$:

$$Y(f, \tau_0) = A \sum_{k,l,n=-\infty}^{+\infty} C_{klm} \delta(f - (k+l)f_b - m(2f_b)) \quad (13)$$

where:

$$C_{klm} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(v) j_k(\beta_{\tau_1} v) j_l(\beta_{\mu_1} v) j_m(\beta_{\mu_2} v) dv \quad (14)$$

Furthermore C_{klm} can be evaluated using mean value theorem as:

$$C_{klm} \approx \Delta f \cdot j_k(\beta_{\tau_1} f_c) j_l(\beta_{\mu_1} f_c) j_m(\beta_{\mu_2} f_c) P(f_c) \quad (15)$$

The Δf is pulse bandwidth. In (15) states that the slow time spectrum contains spectral lines at frequencies of harmonics for breathing frequency as it is discrete.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A twenty six-year-old guy remained motionless in the space behind the wall first study. A naturally breathing man's reaction was recorded over a 20-second cycle when the man was standing still. The fact that a chest of human moves produces differing radar proceeds with various back-scattering amplitudes is well established. A dimensional model was created by removing the scene's sequential range profiles in order to plot this shift in the setting. Static artefacts. The radar images displayed in Figure 5 are the product of this shift detection process. The breathing man's time-varying differential range-profiles are then sequentially shown to create a 2D diagram, as seen in Figure 5(a). For all time instants in the snapshot, changes across the 30 cm range distance can be easily identified [24], [25].

The answer at 30 cm range is depicted in Figure 5(b) in relation to the observed time period. The figure shows a total of 7 breathings (over a 16-second period), which is compatible with nominal breathing values for a safe person. The monitoring of heartbeats was the subject of the second study. For this reason, the individual stood still for 16 seconds just behind the wall, keeping his breath.

Figure 5. Radar objects for breathing people: (a) a 2D picture generated by sequentially viewing variance profiles of ranges and (b) a slice of the resulting copy corresponding to the 30 cm range

The experimental set-up and parameters remained unchanged from the previous experiment. Figure 6 shows the radar photos that resulted. The only difference in the scene was his pounding heart, so the individual was not able to breathe (and therefore his chest was at rest). As opposed to the breathing experiment, the time-varying range-profiles with poorer reflection were observed and plotted as a two-dimensional radar picture in Figure 6(a). Changes in the picture at a 50 dB amplitude level can be seen at

30 cm spectrum diameter. The plot in Figure 6 is the product of scheming the answer at 30 cm range space against the practical time period (b). The peaks in this graph refer to the person's heartbeats. A total of 18 peaks were found, corresponding to 64 pulses per minute. This finding is compatible with a balanced man's nominal heart rate of 60 to 80 beats per minute.

Figure 6. Heartbeat radar portraits: (a) a 2D picture generated by sequentially viewing the sequential profiles-of-ranges and (b) a slice of the resulting copy corresponding to the 30 centimeter set of possibilities

5. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have effectively illustrated the capacity of radar to identify life sign symptoms via the wall. The suggested procedure, which employs a shift detection algorithm, successfully identifies and locates the human's location as well as periodic breathing and pulse motion. The findings of the experiment demonstrate that the breathing and pulse speeds detected are in line with nominal values for a safe individual. Our process is highly accurate and simple to use. This technique can quickly be applied to find survivors trapped under disaster debris and other related uses.

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